

MODELLING THE SIGNATURE OF HUMAN INFLUENCE ON VEGETATION DYNAMIC IN KAMUKU NATIONAL PARK, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The sustainable development goal (SDG 15) recognizes the necessity to investigate important biodiversity because of human disturbance. This research models the signature of human influence on vegetation dynamics in the protected area. The Vegetation Index 16-Day from MODIS was used. A novel method for computing the vegetation deficit index (standardized vegetation deficit index: SVDI) on a 3 to 24 month scale was proposed. In addition, NDVI and VCI were used to assess the vegetation condition. Time series decomposition, Mann-Kendall, coefficient of variance, landscape fragmentation matrix, correlation, and wavelet analysis were used. Key informant interviews were conducted to assess the socioeconomic and driving factors of vegetation changes. The findings revealed that across all five period scales of SVDI, and the wavelet result in the last decade, human activities have had a tremendous footprint on the vegetation dynamics. It was also revealed that because of the insecurity that happened in the area, there was vegetation regeneration (from 2015 to 2021), which was revealed in the result of vegetation indices and their spectrum. The changes in vegetation revealed by this studies were justified by the changes perceived by the communities around the national park. The community's livelihood activities were hampered because of the occurrence of insecurity in and around the national park.

Keyword: SDVI, Insecurity, landscape matrix, VCI, Regeneration, Livelihood, wavelet analysis

INTRODUCTION

Ecosystem provide services that humans rely on for livelihood and well-being (Weiskopf et al., 2020; Salvati et al., 2019; Sintayehu, 2018; Weiskopf et al., 2020). These include supplies of oxygen, food, water, fiber, shelter and fuel, as well as cultural services. It also provides recreational and tourism potential (Alleway et al., 2019; Manea et al., 2019). Nigeria is one of Africa's most biodiverse countries due to its unique geographic location, which includes a wide range of climates and natural ecosystems. These include semi-arid, forested environments, rich seasonal flood plain environments, vast freshwater swamp, and diverse coastal vegetation (Adedeji et al., 2020; Oyebanji et al., 2021) that are thriving for attraction to eco-hospitality resorts. It also provides medical herbs and food (Ijeomah et al., 2018; Wearing et al., 2020). These potential has led to the establishment of national parks in Nigeria with the objective of preserving, enhancing, protecting, and managing the vegetation and wildlife in the parks (Adora, 2010; Dutse, 2013; Ijeomah et al., 2018; Ijeomah & Henry, 2012). Nigeria national park authority has continued to prioritize the protection of its resources, park facilities, and tourist safety, all of which are of exceptional biological, scientific, and economic value. It has a diverse range of fauna and flora, as well as natural

resources and cultural features. Apart from the major role of protecting the ecotourism resources in the national parks and protected areas, they also play an important role in meeting the needs of underprivileged people who live in and around them and rely heavily on forest resources for survival (Adenle, et al., 2020). This is extremely common in rural areas where there are few economic opportunities (Ijeomah & Henry, 2012; Yazdanpanah et al., 2016). These parks' values span from the preservation of natural habitats and accompanying flora and wildlife to the preservation of environmental stability in their surrounding areas. Furthermore, they give a unique field that includes a variety of sectors such as conservation education, regional economic development, and sustainable resource use, as well as job creation, revenue generation, research, and monitoring (Abdulkadir, 2015; Ijeomah & Henry, 2012).

The life of the nearby population is entirely reliant on the national park's resources. It explains their irrigation, livestock husbandry, water, forestry, and agricultural project successes (Agyeman, 2014; Ijeomah et al., 2018; Ijeomah & Henry, 2012). However, the continues rise in the human population and demand is putting a strain on ecosystem resources such as forests, water, and soil. For example, the requirement for increased agricultural output depletes surface and groundwater resources, leading to deforestation, overgrazing, and timber overcutting, among other things (Eruotor, 2014; Nababa et al., 2020; Olagbaiye et al., 2021)(Why different font). The park is now faced with threats such as illegal grazing, poaching, shifting cultivation, over-exploitation of indigenous plant species, cattle migration, and uncontrolled poaching (Osinubi et al., 2021). Also, bushfires, decrease in fauna population, exploitation of fuel wood, fishing, and high timber demand are related problems in the park (Ajayi & Oyejade, 2021).

Furthermore, the increasing loss of vegetal resources and its impact on the loss of biodiversity and the provision of ecosystem services has increased international concern. It stresses the formulation of sustainable development goal fifteen (SDG 15), which states that there is a need to monitor and identify the current status of biodiversity due to the global biodiversity declines in recent decades because of human alteration (Herrero et al., 2021; Viana et al., 2022). This has given rise to the need for continued assessment and monitoring of biodiversity, especially the vegetal cover and its dynamics, because it plays a crucial role in maintaining the functioning of the earth's diverse ecosystems (Nababa et al., 2020; Sintayehu, 2018). However, a growing number of studies have shown that vegetation growth has been strongly altered by human activities in recent decades (Essien & Cyrus, 2019; LV et al., 2020; Obiahu & Elias, 2020; Zaharaddeen et al., 2017). Considering the security challenges in the area as a result of the proliferation of arms, which increased the tension in the communities around the park (Babagana et al., 2019; Bala & Tar, 2021). National park has become a safe haven for bandits,

which has influenced the activity in or around the park due to safety reasons. (Ajayi & Oyebade, 2021).

This study focused on Kamuku National Park because it is one of the seven national parks that contain the major ecotourism resources in Nigeria (Abdulkadir, 2015; Allu, 2015; Okonkwo, 2014). The park was established in 1936 as the Forest Reserve by the Northern Nigeria Government and was upgraded from a state Game Reserve to a National Park in May 1999 (Abdulkadir, 2015; Adora, 2010). In North West Nigeria, Kamuku National Park is one of the best remaining blocks of Sudan-Guinea Savannah vegetation, with high incidences of insecurity (Oladeji et al., 2021). In addition, the research is based on the hypothesis that the increased incidence of insecurity has reduced the influence of human activities in the protected area, especially on its vegetation dynamics, and enhances the potential resources for ecotourism. Therefore, it assesses its dynamism using remote sensing indices and qualitative analysis. It also proposed a novel method, which is to standardize the vegetation deficit index by using the vegetation indices and an appropriate distribution function by identifying the extreme disturbances of human activities to the vegetation. This has been accompanied by a landscape fragmentation matrix and wavelet analysis to assess the level of vegetation deterioration in the national park. In addition, the time series decomposition was applied to separate the trends, seasonal and residue. This allows one to determine whether there is regeneration or degeneration of vegetation dynamics in the national park using a trend test.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Kamuku National Park is located in the north-west part of Birnin-Gwari, The park lies between longitudes 6.15° E and 6.65° E and latitudes 10.68° N and 11.05° N, within the Northern Guinea Savanna Zone, with the mean annual rainfall of 1250 mm. The rainy season is between April and October, while the dry season lasts from November to March. Temperatures range between 30 and 35 degrees Celsius and can reach 42 degrees Celsius in March and April. The park lies within the basement complex region of Nigeria with shallow ferruginous loams and clay soils with areas of overlying laterite (Abdulkadir, 2015). The average weathered zone is less than 20 m frequently outcropping at the surface (Abdulkadir, 2015; Ijeomah et al., 2011).

Global NDVI dataset

The Vegetation indices of 16-Day composite NetCDF file format from MODIS onboard the Terra platform (MOD13Q1) product was downloaded using Google Earth Engine (GEE). It was atmospherically corrected and the images were smoothed utilizing a Whittaker smoother algorithm. The smoothed MODIS NDVI data was converted to the WGS24 global projection. The spatial resolution of the data was resampled to a 30 m dataset. The maximum value composite (MVC) method was applied to the original time series to resample monthly NDVI datasets for further analysis.

Method

The NDVI is a Modis global free data set, which was obtained using the Google Earth engine. The vegetation condition index and standardized vegetation deficit index were computed using Python in a Jupyter notebook environment. In addition, statistical analyses such as variability, trend, correlation analysis, and wavelet analysis were conducted. The Python libraries used in conducting this analysis are Numpy, Pandas, Xarray, Rioxarray, Geopandas,

Cartopy, Matplotlib, Statsmodels, Scipy, and Pymannkendall. Furthermore, the Landscape Ecology Statistics (LecoS) which is an extension of QGIS software was used for landscape analysis. The procedure of the method in this research is explained in this section.

Indices computation for the analysis

The NDVI dataset was obtained from global free data, but normally it can be computed as follows:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED}$$

The processed NDVI data were subjected to various algorithms in order to compute additional indices such as the vegetation condition index and the standardized vegetation deficit index. that NDVI, VCI, and SVDI can reveal the vigor, condition, deficit, and health of vegetation. From the smoothed NDVI long-term time series (2000–2021), the Vegetation Condition Index (VCI) for the study area was calculated using the following equation:

$$VCI = \left(\frac{NDVI_i - NDVI_{min}}{NDVI_{max} - NDVI_{min}} \right) \times 100\%$$

Where NDVI_i is the monthly NDVI value, NDVI_{max} and NDVI_{min} are the absolute long-term maximum and minimum NDVI respectively calculated for each pixel and monthly from multi-year NDVI data and i defines the NDVI for the ith month.

The standardized vegetation deficit index was computed based on the standardized precipitation index (SPI) procedure. Therefore, it is assumed as a probability index, which considers NDVI as the input. Initially, the gamma distribution was used to fit the long-term NDVI data using the following equation:

$$f(NDVI; \alpha; \beta) = \frac{1}{\beta^\alpha \Gamma(\alpha)} NDVI^{\alpha-1} e^{-NDVI/\beta} \text{ for } NDVI, \alpha, \beta > 0$$

Where, α and β are the shape and scale parameters respectively; and Γ(α) is the gamma function. The resulting parameters were then used to derive the cumulative probability for non-zero NDVI using the following equation:

$$F(NDVI; \alpha; \beta) = \int_0^{NDVI} f(NDVI; \alpha; \beta) dNDVI$$

Then

$$F(NDVI; \alpha; \beta) = \frac{1}{\beta^\alpha \Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^{NDVI} NDVI^{\alpha-1} e^{-NDVI/\beta} dNDVI$$

The cumulative probability was transformed into a standardized normal distribution so that the SVDI mean and variance were zero and one, respectively. The current study employed the approximate transformations provided by Mishra and Desai (2006) to transform the cumulative probability distribution into a standardized normal distribution, which were given in equations:

$$SVDI = - \left(K - \frac{c_0 + c_1k + c_2k^2}{1 + d_1k + d_2k^2 + d_3k^3} \right)$$

When $k = \sqrt{\ln \left(\frac{1}{(H(NDVI))^2} \right)}$ for $0 < H(NDVI) \leq 0.5$

$$SVDI = + \left(K - \frac{c_0 + c_1k + c_2k^2}{1 + d_1k + d_2k^2 + d_3k^3} \right)$$

When $k = \sqrt{\ln \left(\frac{1}{(H(NDVI))^2} \right)}$ for $0 < H(NDVI) \leq 0.5$

Where, $c_0 = 2.515517$, $c_1 = 0.802853$, $c_2 = 0.010328$, $d_1 = 1.432788$, $d_2 = 0.189269$, $d_3 = 0.001308$. The SVDI values were calculated for multiple monthly time scales (3, 6, 9, 12, and 24-month time scales). In this study, the SDVI is used to identify the footprint of human activities on vegetation. If the period of high vegetation vigor coincides with the period when intense insecurity happens in the area, then it implies that the prior period is the period of human activities affecting the vegetation vigor.

Computation of Vegetation fragmentation

A threshold of greater than 0.2 vegetation indices (NDVI) was used to delineate the distribution of vegetation and exposed soil.

This result was subjected to landscape metrics to determine the level of deterioration and regeneration of vegetation in the national park. For landscape analysis, the Landscape Ecology Statistics (LecoS) extension of QGIS software was used. The landscape metrics indices that were used are presented in table 1.

Statistical analysis

Variability analysis involves the use of the coefficient of variation (CV) of inter-annual data of vegetation indices. The coefficient of variation (CV) will provide a measure of year-to-year variation in the vegetation index. The CV is expressed as:

$$\overline{NDVI} = \frac{\sum NDVI}{N}$$

$$SD_{NDVI} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (X - \overline{NDVI})^2}{N}}$$

$$CV = \frac{SD_{NDVI}}{\overline{NDVI}} \times 100$$

Where:

- NDVI = Yearly NDVI variable
- N = Number of years in the sample
- SD = Standard Deviation
- CV = Coefficient of Variance

Table 1: The Selected Landscape Matrix Indices

Analysis scale	Metrics
Class	Landscape Proportion
Class	Edge density
Landscape/Class	Mean patch area
Landscape/Class	Number of Patches
Landscape/Class	Largest Patch Index
Landscape/Class	Overall Core area
Landscape/Class	Fractal Dimension Index
Landscape/Class	Mean patch shape ratio
Landscape/Class	Patch cohesion index
Landscape/Class	Effective Meshsize
Landscape/Class	Splitting Index
Landscape	Shannon Diversity index
Landscape	Shannon equitability index
Landscape	Simpson index

Source: author compilation

Time series analysis

Time series decomposition was conducted to reveal the time series characteristics of the indices. These characteristics include trends, seasonality, and residues. To achieve this, the following equation was used:

$$Data = pattern + error + \begin{cases} \rightarrow f(trend) \\ - cycle, seasonality, error) \end{cases}$$

Therefore

$$Y_t = f(St, Tt, Et)$$

Additive decomposition

$$Y_t = St + Tt + Et$$

Multiplicative decomposition

$$Y_t = St * Tt * Et$$

Subsequently, the Mann-Kendall (M-K) rank correlation test was used to determine the direction and significance of the trend in vegetation indices. A detailed procedure for Mann Kendall can be

found in the (Abdussalam & Zaharaddeen, 2017; Ismail et al., 2019; Zaharaddeen et al., 2017). In addition, a correlation analysis between the monthly values of NDVI, VCI and SVDI for time-scales from 3 to 24 months was performed. For each grid cell, the maximum correlation coefficient was retained and assessed as significant if a P-value less than 0.05.

Wavelet analysis

Wavelet analysis is the time localization of the spectral components that transform the time–frequency of the signal. This was done by decomposing signals in such a way that the signal trends and details are represented in time. Therefore, the variation of their amplitude with time is plotted to extract regions of strong concentration of power. The major reason for considering the wavelet transform for this work is that it is a robust method for signal analysis. It is used to identify the high signal and periodicity of a variable spectrum. A more detailed theoretical background of wavelet analysis can be found in the work of Adepitan & Falayi, (2019); Baidu et al., (2017). In this study, the scaled averaged wavelet power is used to present the fluctuations in power over the most significant frequency of vegetation vigor that is obtained from the global wavelet power spectrum. This allows us to identify the period with high vegetation vigor as a result of human activities being reduced due to insecurity. Therefore, if the period coincides with the period when the intense insecurity happens in the area, then it implies that the prior period is the period of human activities affecting the vegetation vigor.

Socio economic characteristics and drivers of vegetation changes information

The information on the drivers of vegetation changes, the contribution and extent of the security issues to the community destruction and their livelihoods, as well as the vegetation cover changes, were obtained using key informant interviews. During the interviews, questions were translated into the native language in order to get an appropriate response. Some of the questions were: what are the social characteristics of people (majority in gender, age, education level, occupation, and others); what is their economic status (an average income level)? What are the major activities they depend on for their livelihood (such as farming, trading, lumbering, and others)? How do these activities contribute to the vegetation's dynamism (does it increase or decrease the vegetation)? What are the major challenges that affect their livelihood (concerning vegetation change and insecurity)? How do they think that these challenges have influenced the vegetation dynamic? What do they think are the causes of vegetation change? What are the consequences of the vegetation change within the area? The responses were carefully categorized based on the thematic areas to have a clear elucidation and harmonized information that was discussed. The thematic areas are: socio-economic characteristics, major activities for livelihood, drivers for vegetation changes, nature of insecurity and its influence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Inter Annual Variability of Vegetation Dynamics

The annual variability of vegetation dynamics in Kamuku national park was assessed from 2000–2021 using NDVI, SVDI and VCI. Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis were used to describe the inter-annual variability (table 1) and the relationship between the indices (table 2), respectively.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Vegetation Dynamics Indices

Indices	Min	Max	Mean	Var	STD
SVDI 24	-1.72	0.98	0.01	0.38	0.61
SVDI 12	-1.02	0.73	0.07	0.21	0.46
SVDI 9	-7.51	5.86	0.54	12.91	3.59
SVDI 6	-0.44	0.30	0.03	0.05	0.22
SVDI 3	-0.36	0.24	0.02	0.03	0.17
VCI	58.27	63.39	61.30	1.75	1.32
NDVI	0.46	0.52	0.50	0.00	0.02

Table 2: Relationship between the Vegetation Dynamic Indices

Indices	SVDI 24	SVDI 9	SVDI 12	SDVI 6	SVDI 3	VCI	NDVI
SVDI 24	1						
SVDI 9	0.411	1					
SVDI 12	0.621	0.705	1				
SVDI 6	0.189	0.695	0.421	1			
SVDI 3	0.011	0.516	0.242	0.800	1		
VCI	-0.042	0.463	0.189	0.726	0.905	1	
NDVI	-0.042	0.463	0.189	0.726	0.905	1.000	1

The variation of NDVI of the entire Kamuku national park is illustrated in table 1. It was discovered that the NDVI indicated a high level of vegetation vigor in the study area. Similarly, the area has a healthier vegetation condition (VCI > 50), as the forest and conserved area is still maintaining its natural regeneration. In addition, it can be clearly seen that the level of decline was low in SVDI 9 months, while the remaining SVDI showed a near normal level of decline in vegetation in the study area.

In addition, the correlation coefficient was used to establish the relationship between the indices under study (table 2) because it measures the degree of association between the variables (Olson et al., 2019; Roustia et al., 2020). It was also revealed that the standardized vegetation deficit index of 9 months has a significant relationship with the other indices, though it was weak in the relationship with the NDVI and VCI. The SVDI 6 month had a strong relationship with the SVDI 3 month, NDVI and VCI, although the SVDI 3 month had the strongest relationship with the NDVI and VCI.

to 2022 with a period between 8 and 16 months (figure 6F).

Figure 1: Inter Annual Spatial

Variability of Vegetation Condition

Furthermore, the spatial inter-annual variability of vegetation conditions in Kamuku National Park was assessed using coefficient variability from 2000 to 2021 (figure 1). It was revealed that the majority and core area of the study area had low variability of vegetation cover, whereas the border of the study area had high variability, with the exception of the south-east of the study area. This implies that the vegetation condition at the border of the study area is more deteriorated than the core of the area. The time series of the standardized vegetation deficit index was plotted to show the extent of the variability and possible regeneration of the vegetation in the study area (figure 2). The SVDI 3 month shows a fluctuation in vegetation deficit. Similarly, the 6 and 9 months SVDI revealed a fluctuation of vegetation condition, while the 12 and 24 months SVDI revealed a clear temporal transition of vegetation condition from decline to regeneration. It is obvious that the vegetation regenerated around 2018 to 2021. The time series decomposition of the vegetation indices was computed to check the trend, seasonality, and residue (figure 3). It revealed that the standardized vegetation deficit index of the vegetation condition has a positive trend, which implies an increased trend. While the vegetation condition index and normalized difference vegetation index showed no trend. However, the trend observed in SVDI was not significant, yet figure 4 also shows that the vegetation conditions were disrupted from 2009 to 2013, while from 2014 to 2021 there was a recovery of vegetation conditions in the I park. The wavelet analysis was conducted on the NDVI and SDVI to identify the high frequency of signal (figure 6A-F). It is evident that the high frequency of the NDVI spectrum was from 2001 to 2007 and from 2015 to 2020, with a periodicity of between 8 and 16 months (figure 6A). The SDVI 3, 6, and 9-month had a homogeneity of high frequency from 2000 to 2021, with a 16-month periodicity (figure 6B-6D). In addition, figure 6E revealed that the SDVI 12 month has a high frequency from 2000 to 2002 and from 2009 to 2020 with a period of 16 months, while the SDVI 24 month has a high magnitude from 2000 to 2003 and from 2011 to 2018 and up

Figure 2: Standardize vegetation deficit index (a) 3 month (b) 6 month (c) 9 month (d) 12 month and (e) 24 month

Figure 3: time series decomposition of the vegetation indices under study: (A) SVDI 24 (B) SVDI 12 (C) SVDI 9 (D) SVDI 6 (E) SVDI 3 (F) VCI and (G) NDVI

Seasonal variability of vegetation dynamics in Kamuku National Park

The seasonal variation of vegetation dynamics in Kamuku National Park was assessed using the normalized difference vegetation index, vegetation condition index, and standardized vegetation deficit index. The result revealed that the level of vegetation has varied across seasons (figure 4a). The high NDVI value was recorded in autumn while the low NDVI value was obtained in winter (DJF). The level of vegetation is obviously declining in SDVI 12 months in the winter and spring (figure 4B). It was also revealed that a high deficit of vegetation was observed across seasons. The healthier vegetation was identified in the autumn (SON) season, while the most disrupted vegetation was in the winter and spring. Despite the general condition of the vegetation observed (figures 4a, b, and c), it is obvious that the level and magnitude of encroachment into the national park can be seen in the west-south direction.

Further SDVI of 3, 6, 9 and 24 months of vegetation was assessed (figure 5). The level of deficit of vegetation was high during the dry season (DJF: Winter, MAM: Spring) as compared to the rainy season (JJA: Summer, SON: Autumn), especially for 3 and 6 months (figure 5A and B). However, within the 6 months, the level of healthier vegetation was observed in winter, followed by the autumn season. As the lag of a month shifted for the standardized vegetation deficit index from three to nine, the level of the deficit varied from one season to the others.

Fragmentation of Vegetation in Kamuku National Park

The landscape metrics reporting the level of fragmentation of vegetation in the study area. The dominance indices (Landscape Proportion, Largest Patch Index, and Overall Core area) of the vegetation condition indicates that there was gradual increase of these indices from 2015 to 2021 with a positive trend. Therefore, the dominance indices indicated that there is more vegetation during the period, (regeneration period between 2015 and 2021). The Edge density, mean patch area, Number of Patches and Patch cohesion index result are shows in figure 7. It revealed that there is decreased of Edge density towards 2021, with a negative trend. Mean patch area also revealed a gradual increased and a significant trend, which implies that a high value of Mean patch indicates low fragmentation while a low value indicates high fragmentation. In addition, the Number of Patches shows a low value for the vegetation in the study area. The result revealed a gradual decreased of Patch cohesion index in the study area. Furthermore, the landscape metric reflects the complexity in the study area. The mean patch shape ratio has a higher value towards 2021, with a sharp increase. It also revealed a significant positive trend in the study area. In addition, the Fractal Dimension Index and Effective Meshsize revealed a positive trend, which implies an increased trend in the study area. While the Splitting Index has a negative trend and a gradual decline towards 2021. To provide information on the diversity in the study area, the Shannon diversity index, Shannon equitability index, and Simpson index were used (figure 7). It revealed an increase in diversity, as well as an increasingly equitable distribution of landscape area

Figure 4: Seasonal variation of (A) NDVI (B) SVDI (C) VCI

Figure 5: Seasonal variation of SVDI (A) 3 month (B) 6 month (C) 9 month (D) 24 month

Figure 6: wavelet spectrum of (A) NDVI (B) SDVI 3 (C) SDVI 6 (D) SDVI 9 (E) SDVI 12 and (F) SDVI 24 month in Kamuku national park, Nigeria

Figure 7: fragmentation index of vegetation in Kamuku

Socio economic characteristics and drivers of vegetation cover changes

The respondent interviews reported that the majority of the people that were actively involved in the activities around the park were youths (male and female). Early marriage has greatly contributed to the population around the park, the communities surrounding the national park are majorly polygamous, with an average of twelve people per house. Furthermore, the majority of the community were those with no formal education, though few had education up to the tertiary level. It was also revealed that the occupations of people living in communities around the Park are farming, logging, trading, mining, fishing, and blacksmithing among others. Although farming was their major occupation because they inherited it from their parents, the rural community in northern Nigeria mostly depends on farming as their major source of livelihood because of the availability of large land areas suitable for farming (Adenle et al., 2020; Adepoju et al., 2019).

They reported that the major insecurity in the area was kidnapping, banditry, cattle rustling, and arm robbery. The park served as a hideout for people engaged in these cruel, unhuman activities. They ascertained that, as such, their activities for livelihood have been detrimental and some of the communities had to evacuated. The respondents also reported that the incidences of insecurity that are happening in the area have deteriorated the status of livelihoods in the local government. The respondents lamented that the insecurity is heightening due to the presence of dense vegetation in the area and Kamuku national park in particular, especially since the park is adjoined with the Kwiambana forest in a neighboring state.

The intensity and severity of insecurity occurred more frequently around 2014 up to date. It was established that it started as arm robbery and escalated to cattle rustling, the cattle rustlers move from one locality to another, rustling the communities' cattle. Subsequently, a more frequent and deadly occurrences is the banditry and kidnappings are happening in the area. The response is that the majority of the localities around the Kamuku national park are being wiped away, and the people had to relocate to the nearby town (some of these localities are Gwaska, Kungi, Kwasakwa, Nabango, Layin Maigwari, Old Birnin Gwari among others). Furthermore, the respondents interviewed confirmed that they had noticed changes in vegetation cover in the park, especially at its boundary. It is believed that the population increase around the park may have influenced the changes in vegetation cover and, consequently, the biodiversity in general (LV et al., 2020; Nwilo et al., 2020). The majority of respondents alluded that human activities such as agriculture, fuel wood harvesting, charcoal production, logging, and bush burning are the primary drivers of vegetation cover changes in the park. They emphasized that agricultural activities was one of the major causes of vegetation cover changes, which was expected to result in biodiversity loss. They lamented that due to the farming practices around the park, there could also be destruction of land and deforestation. This is because most farmers in rural communities in Nigeria often engage in slash and burn when cultivating the land, which could lead to the loss of many species (Dussol et al., 2021; Ketterings et al., 1999; Tschakert et al., 2007).

Logging, fuel wood harvesting, and charcoal production also contribute immensely to driving forest change. It affects the sustainability of forest cover as well as biodiversity. The responders lamented that bush burning is seen as a factor that causes vegetation changes, as it's an act of setting the natural forest on fire by man in search of food (such as rabbits, bush rats, and many more). Moreover, they reported that mining is also regarded as a factor that affects vegetation cover, many of these natural minerals resources are found in the park for different reasons of accumulation, compaction, and cementation of different components.

The result of the study revealed that the vegetation declined from 2003 to 2015, while there was regeneration of vegetation up to 2020. This result is similar to that of Adepoju et al., (2019), who found that the vegetation had declined in the savanna. Also, Yager et al., (2022); Hula, (2010) and Adenle et al., (2020) found a decrease in vegetation in Cross River State, Benue State, and the Nigerian Guinea Savanna at large, respectively and this attributed to human activities such as agriculture, illegal logging and fuel wood harvesting which has contributed to the decrease in vegetation. Several studies state that human activities play a significant role in vegetation dynamics (Cai et al., 2015; He et al., 2015; Isa & Danjuma, 2018; Naeem et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2016). According to the Udofia and Udoh, (2021), conducted a study in the southern part of Nigeria and found that agriculture was the major human activity affecting the vegetation cover and its resources. Illegal logging and fuel wood harvesting were reported as key causes of vegetation changes (Cai et al., 2015). Musa & Solomon, (2011) reported that mining activities contributed to vegetation decline in Bukuru, Jos Plateau State. Similarly, Khadijat et al., (2021) found that if the current human activities continue, the forest cover will continue to be endangered, thus leading to a decrease in dense forest, plantation, and sparse vegetation in Ibadan, Nigeria. For this reason, it leads to the exposure of land to direct sunlight, rain, and wind storms, which cause soil erosion and degradation, which in turn affect forest productivity (Nwilo et al., 2020; Obiahu & Elias, 2020; Zaharaddeen et al., 2017). In the act or process of harnessing the natural endowment by man, the vegetation tends to be directly affected by the process (Bangira et al., 2019; Mosbahi & Benabdallah, 2020; Obodai et al., 2019). In addition, this result is supported by the perceived changes in vegetation by the respondent during the interview.

The results obtained from the interview, it was revealed that insecurity is an inevitable phenomenon, but if its severity and persistence are high, it affects the development as well as socio economic characteristics and livelihood activities of that particular place. In the area of study, the responder reported that the severity of insecurity was more around 2014 to date. A similar result was found by Chukwuma & Francis, (2014) where they reported that in the presence of insecurity, the activities of that area are affected negatively. For the sake of livelihood, people have to move away from the homes, which proliferated the creation of IDPs (Adora, 2010; Bala & Tar, 2021; Ojo, 2020; Tar & Safana, 2021).

Conclusion

The loss of vegetal resources leading to the loss of biodiversity and the provision of ecosystem services, has generated a great concern for immediate resolution. A proposed novel method of calculating the vegetation deficit index (standardized vegetation deficit index: SVDI) was used. NDVI, VCI, and SVDI were also computed to examine the influence of human activities on

vegetation dynamics. The findings reveal that the last decade has had a tremendous footprint of human activities on the vegetation dynamics. It revealed that due to the insecurity happening in the area, there is vegetation regeneration, which is revealed by the results of vegetation indices and wavelet results. This might likely leave the mark of the influence of climate change in the park. The community's livelihood activities were hindered because of the occurrence of insecurity in and around the national park. The changes in vegetation observed in the studies were justified by the changes perceived by the communities around the national park. As a result, this study provides a baseline for the state of protected areas as well as an updated time series of vegetation changes. The approach used in this study may be applied in other protected areas in Nigeria and the world at large to assess the status of vegetation dynamics.

Ethical requirement

The research is conducted on modeling the signature of human activities on vegetation in protected area. A case study of Kamuku national park, Nigeria. Please, your sincere response to these questions are required. Information supplied was use strictly for academic purpose. Any information regarded to personality will not be published. Your assistance and cooperation is highly appreciated.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to acknowledge MODIS, Google Group and the Python developer and it libraries for providing the data, and tools used for this study. In addition, the authors acknowledge the sponsorship provided by TETFund through Kaduna State University for this research.

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